

Constrained Randomness in Musical Form Using Quantum Computational Algorithms

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Abstract. *The balance between chaos and order, constraint and freedom have been a long-discussed topic in the context of music composition. Algorithms and stochastic models are being used widely by composers, to create constraints. Stochastic models enable the probabilistic events to be constrained within a framework, to achieve the possible results with a degree of freedom. Discoveries in the field of quantum computing offer new areas of application of probabilistic models in the field of music. Inspired by the ideas of spectral music, this article aims to show how quantum computational algorithms can be used to achieve constrained randomness in musical form, by applying the probabilistic nature of quantum circuits to compose an electronic music piece.*

1 Introduction

The idea of constraints is one of the core aspects of music composition. Each music piece is constrained within its formal structure. Composer I. Stravinsky addressed the idea of musical constraint as: “The more constraints one imposes, the more one frees one’s self. . . and the arbitrariness of the constraint serves only to obtain precision of execution.” [1]. In 20th Century, the contributions of composers such as A. Schoenberg and J. Schillinger, enabled the conscious application of algorithms and mathematical operations in music, to create musical constraints [2].

Since then, the use of algorithms in composition had various applications in the last century. M. Babbitt’s time-point system utilized the 12-tone series to determine the attack point of each note [3]. C. Wuorinen adapted this system, to determine the durations of each formal section, enabling an interconnection between smaller and larger formal elements [3]. Finally, R. Reynolds has explored the applications of chaos theory in musical form, using Hénon map as a basis of form for his work *Dionysus (1990)* [4].

Even though purely algorithmic constraints have its use in composition, composers have searched for the balance between constraint and freedom, determinacy and indeterminacy in various ways. In K. Stockhausen’s words, the search for “series of degrees of freedom” [5] lead to ideas such as J. Cage’s aleatoric music and I. Xenakis’ “stochastic music”. The “arbitrariness of the constraint” presents itself vividly in “stochastic music”, which utilizes probabilistic algorithms to make compositional decisions.

Since the idea of stochasticity is closely related with quantum mechanics, with the current explorations in the field of quantum computing, it is now possible to use

quantum computational algorithms as a mean of stochastic music. E. R. Miranda and S. Basak have developed an algorithm using the constructive and destructive interference [6] property of quantum physics, to create note sequences using the options on a Markov chain [7]. S. Souma has explored the possible representation of musical progressions in terms of quantum gates and proposed a stochastic note sequence generation model using quantum circuits [8]. E. R. Miranda and H. Miller-Bakewell have showed how cellular automata music can be adapted to quantum computing [9]. E. J. Allen, J. F. F. Bulmer and S. D. Small have processed the measurement outcomes of quantum computational algorithms to create melodies as a basis for composition [10].

In the foregoing cited studies, the researchers were mainly focused on stochastic decision making in smaller formal elements of music. This article aims to show how the quantum computational algorithms can be used to achieve constrained randomness in the larger form of a music piece.

2 Method

To show the possible application of quantum computational algorithms for an indeterminately controlled formal structuring, an electronic music piece is composed for demonstration¹.

2.1 Formal Structure

The formal structure of the piece stems from the idea of “statistical acceleration” of musical events in time, presented by the composer G. Grisey [11], as it represents a good example for controlled randomness (Figure 1). According to this method, the overall structure of acceleration is maintained, but the fluctuations in the timing of each event provide statistical, indeterminate changes between musical events, thus creating a *surprise factor*.

2.1.1 Temporal Structure

To formalize the statistical acceleration, the following equation is used:

$$\text{duration of event } i = f^{d^i} \text{ for } i = 0, 1, \dots, n \quad (1)$$

where

$$d = \sqrt[n]{\frac{l}{f}} \quad (2)$$

¹The composed piece, *Schweigen (2023)* is available at <https://github.com/erenutku97/Schweigen>

Figure 1: A representation of G. Grisey’s idea of statistical acceleration. The dashed line shows the ideal acceleration, and the continuous line, the statistical acceleration of musical events

is the decrement; f , l are the durations of the first and last event; and n is the total number of events minus one.

For this composition, each event represents a chord, hence the duration of each event is the duration of each chord. The first chord duration is designated as 13 s and the last chord duration as 0.55 s.

To apply quantum indeterminacy to the temporal structure, the Quantum Audio Python module is used [12]. The module can represent audio signals as quantum circuits and run these circuits using Qiskit (an open-source software development kit for quantum computing) [13] simulations. While the module is mainly built for quantum representation of audio signals, it can be used for representing any function as probability amplitudes using QPAM (Quantum Probability Amplitude Modulation) [14]. In the context of temporal structure, this may represent the probability amplitude of each musical event, having the same duration obtained in Equation 1. In this case, the degree of indeterminacy of the musical process can be controlled by setting the number of *shots* (or trials) for the calculation of the quantum circuit. As the number of shots increase, the probabilistic durations would approach the calculated durations.

To represent Equation 1 in terms of a quantum circuit, the total number of events ($n + 1$) is set as:

$$\text{total number of events (chords)} = 2^{\text{number of qubits}} \quad (3)$$

For the composition to have a total duration of approximately 6 mins, with the given first and final event durations, 7 qubits are required. This results in a total of 128 musical events or in this case, 128 chords.

Figure 2 shows the plot of Equation 1, and its QPAM representation with 2^{12} shots. Lower numbers of shots turned out to be prone to large and undesired errors for this function. It must be noted that, to get the given temporal structure with QPAM, the calculation was run sev-

Figure 2: Plot of Equation 1 and its QPAM result

eral times, until an *aesthetically viable* temporal progress is achieved. The aesthetical viability is of course, an artistic choice rather than an algorithmic limitation. Therefore, this stochastic approach with quantum algorithms also enables artistic freedom to some extent.

2.2 Harmonic Structure

Since the temporal structure of the piece is inspired from spectral music, for the harmonic structure, the harmonic series is used. For calculating the harmonic series, the following equation is used [15]:

$$f_p = f_0 \cdot p^e \quad \text{for } p = 1, 2, 3, \dots \quad (4)$$

where f_0 is the frequency of the fundamental, f_p is the frequency of the partial, p is the partial number and e is the exponent. For $e > 1$, the partials are stretched; for $e < 1$, the partials are compressed.

To represent the acceleration of events in the harmonic structure, the process is designated as a spectral compression of harmonic series going linearly from an exponent of $e = 2.7$ to $e = 0.125$ for each consecutive musical event, with 55 Hz (A1) as the fundamental.

The same process used for temporal structure is also applied to the harmonic structure using QPAM. The exponent for each consecutive spectral chord is shown in Figure 3. For each chord, 15 partial frequencies are used including the fundamental frequency. If the frequency of the partial is greater than 4100 Hz, because of the spectral expansion, the partial is omitted from the chord.

2.3 Text Used in the Composition

The German version of L. Wittgenstein’s *Tractatus logico-philosophicus* [16] is used as the text to be read by a Text to Speech (TTS) model [17] in the composition².

The proposition 6.373 (“Die Welt ist unabhängig von meinem Willen./The world is independent of my will”

²As of 2022, the German version of *Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus* is Public Domain [18]. For the piece, K.C. Clement’s typesetting version [16] is used under Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 3.0 License (CC BY-SA 3.0 US).

Figure 3: Spectral exponents in the linear compression of the spectrum and its QPAM result

[19]) is decided to be the starting point of the piece, since it implies the stochastic idea behind the piece. Then the TTS model reads the propositions until the end of the work.

The text is chosen due to the similarity between the ideas it conveys with comparison to stochastic music and quantum mechanics. As an example, L. Wittgenstein writes about how the “value” of the world should lie outside of all happening and being, since all happening and being are “accidental” [20]. Similarly, I. Xenakis in his article, *The Origins of Stochastic Music*, mentions: “(Art) should aim to lead by a constant point of reference towards that total exaltation in which, unaware of self, the individual will identify with an immediate, rare, vast and perfect truth... This massive truth does not consist in objects, nor feelings, nor sensations; it lies beyond them...” [21]. In the field of quantum mechanics, the scientists are still researching why and how the wave-function behaves. One possible philosophical argument considering Wittgenstein’s ideas could be that this nature of particles lies beyond the particles themselves, since it is “accidental” and “what makes it not accidental cannot lie in the world, for otherwise this would again be accidental” [20].

2.4 Instrumentation and Composition

The instrumentation consists of a subtractive synthesizer pad, arpeggiator and a granular synthesizer, a polyphonic pitch shifter for the vocals made with SuperCollider (Version 3.12.2), a Single Qubit Probability Amplitude Modulations (SQPAM) [14] representation of a square-wave-based bass sound used with SuperCollider client for Python [22] to be manipulated using Qiskit functions. Several timbres for the bass sound were tried out by applying quantum operations such as rotating around the $\cos(\varphi)x + \sin(\varphi)y$ axis and Rx gate. Including the unmanipulated timbre of the bass sound, 4 different bass timbre are synthesized.

To retain from a purely algorithmic composition, envelopes are applied to each track. Each envelope shape acts like a musical gesture or a gate to let the underlying process of music audible at certain moments.

3 Conclusion

To demonstrate the possible application of quantum computational algorithms to achieve constrained randomness in musical form, an electronic music piece is composed.

To reflect the idea of G. Grisey’s “statistical acceleration”, an exponential function is constructed. Using the Python module Quantum Audio, a stochastic approximation of the function is prepared for temporal structuring of the piece, with the help of QPAM representation of the function. The same procedure is repeated for the harmonic structure, in which the spectral compression of stretched harmonic series is used to generate spectral chords.

In comparison to other algorithmic methods for formal structuring of a musical piece [3, 4], the application of quantum computational algorithms allows the composer to set a general rule and then decide how much the overall divergence from the rule will be, by setting different number of *trials*. This way, the composition will have a more unpredictable progression, but still keep the desired general form. In addition, at each execution of the algorithm, a different diversion scheme is obtained, allowing the composers to impose their aesthetical choices. Due to the inherent probabilistic nature of quantum computers, the usage of quantum computational algorithms with real quantum computers will enable a stochastic approach in both computational and compositional levels.

For now, this application of quantum computational algorithms utilized just the simulation of quantum computing in a simple way. In future, more complex stochastic approaches can be used for achieving constrained randomness, thus enabling a high-level formal structuring, using real quantum computers. In addition, other possible quantum audio representations such as SQPAM can also be applied for formal structuring.

With the improvements in quantum computation, more diverse and multi-leveled stochastic models will be possible, allowing unusual approaches in stochastic music.

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